

**DEVELOPMENT OF COMMUNICATIVE COMPETENCE IN FUTURE
OFFICERS IS A CHALLENGING PROBLEM****Z.Sh. Alimardonov**

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Abstract. The article is devoted to the analysis of scientific theoretical resources on the formation of communicative competence in a future officer. In particular, it is shown that the role of its structural components in the development of communicative competence in future officers is important.

Key words: communication, communication, handling, competence, communicative competence, perceptive, communicative, interactive, verbal, nonverbal, motivational, cognitive, perceptual skills, reliability, oral speech skills, written communication skills, extraversion, introversion.

Аннотация. Статья посвящена анализу научно-теоретических ресурсов по формированию коммуникативной компетентности у будущего офицера. В частности, показано, что важна роль ее структурных компонентов в развитии коммуникативной компетентности будущих офицеров.

Ключевые слова: общение, общение, обращение, компетентность, коммуникативная компетентность, перцептивная, коммуникативная, интерактивная, вербальная, невербальная, мотивационная, когнитивная, перцептивные навыки, надежность, навыки устной речи, навыки письменного общения, экстраверсия, интроверсия.

Today, the formation of communicative competence is of great importance in establishing and managing the issues of communication and dealings in human relations. Therefore, it is appropriate to dwell on the content of the concept of communicative competence. The criteria of communicative competence were first published in 1975 by T. Designated by Gordon.

Regarding the concept of communicative competence, definitions have been put forward by the authors based on different approaches: it is knowledge of the language, its behavior, empathy, the ability to act in the object of communication to create a predictive model of the personal characteristics of the subject of communication (adequate self-esteem, social orientation); the ability to orientate in different communication situations; the ability to establish and maintain the necessary relationships with other people; a system of internal

resources necessary to create an effective communicative action in certain situations of interpersonal interaction; adaptation to the situation and fluency in verbal and non-verbal means of social behavior; communicative flexibility, etc.

The problem of formation of professional communicative competence of a person is reflected in many social, psychological and linguistic studies from different perspectives. From the point of view of most sociologists and psychologists (A.A. Bodalev, A.B. Dobrovich, E. Ya. Maliburda, L. A. Petrovskaya, E. V. Rudensky, etc.), communication is the main management skill in business situations. They connect communicative competence, first of all, with the ability to predict, program and manage the social-psychological process of communication of a group, team, team.

Researchers in the field of linguistics and pedagogy (E.A. Arkhipova, E.A. Bistrova, G.G. Gorodilova, I.A.V. Mikhalkina, R.B. Sabatkoev, E.A. Khamraeva) develop communicative competence in speech activities ability, motivational (speech behavior), cognitive (knowledge), operational (elimination of contradictions determined by the content of the training) components as the implementation of communicative behavior. I.N. Agafonova defines communicative competence as "an integral system of mental and behavioral characteristics of a person that contributes to successful communication, i.e., achieving a goal (effective) and being emotionally comfortable for participants (psychologically comfortable)." The following components are distinguished in its structure: cognitive, value-semantic, personal, emotional and behavioral [1].

According to E.V. Rudensky [11], communicative competence consists of the following abilities:

- social-psychological diagnosis of the communicative situation of the communication process;
- social and psychological programming of the communication process based on the uniqueness of the communicative situation;
- implementation of socio-psychological control of communication processes in a communicative situation.

The components of communicative competence, according to I.I. Seregina, are "firstly, the ability to communicate with other people (communication), to constantly maintain the necessary relationships with them, and secondly, to have this semantic information and the ability to work with them. It describes the manager's general and professional knowledge, regardless of the field of activity" [12].

Yu.N.Emelyanov [5], Yu.N.Zhukov [6], N.Yu. Khryashcheva [15] distinguish orientation, psychological knowledge, perceptive abilities as criteria for evaluating communicative competence. This, in turn, leaves the question of communicative ability outside the scope of researchers' views.

T. M. Dridze considers the ability to communicate as the main component of communicative competence. "Here the idea is about the ability to establish and maintain the necessary relationships with people, the readiness of the person to communicate in terms of development and important values, attitudes and related skills. Effectiveness of information exchange that causes specific actions depends on communicative competence" [4].

V.P. Trusov stated that "the concept of communicative competence is similar in its content, but in terms of size it is less than cognitive competence in general, and in terms of meaning it is very close to the traditional term of social intelligence, expressed in adequate ability and by the relationship between another person and this subject with another. is a differentiated reflection" [14].

According to G.M. Andreeva's classification [2], communicative competence is a combination of perceptual, communicative and interactive components of communicative activity, which are:

1. Perceptual component - perception and understanding of the interlocutor's position. It includes the ability to listen to the respondent and hear him, assess the social and psychological mood of communication partners; the ability to observe and adequately interpret verbal and non-verbal signals of communication participants, the group, the ability to use an adequate method of interaction with group or individual respondents, the ability to predict the development of the communication process; the ability to identify and regulate the emotional mood of the group in communication; the ability to engage in communication and organize it without prior preparation (improvisation skills).

2. The communicative component is information exchange. It includes the ability to establish, maintain and complete communication, the skills to perceive and evaluate information, the ability to ask questions, and the skills to overcome communication barriers.

3. Interactive component - interaction. It includes the skills of organizing and managing communication processes (managing the center of attention, group dynamics in communication, encouraging participants in the communication process, encouraging communication activity, etc.), the skills of managing the audience's attention in communication with a changing environment, the ability to establish feedback, and the ability to interpret.

L. V. Makarova [10], taking into account G. M. Andreeva's classification, in turn, defines the main criteria (parameters) describing communicative competence and distinguishes them:

1. Perceptual abilities.
2. Reliability.
3. Oral communication skills.
4. Written communication skills.
5. Potential for communication (extraversion, introversion).

At this point, we will touch on the concept of assertiveness given by L. V. Makarova [10], which is extremely important for us (in fact, like the phenomenon of assertiveness itself).

Assertiveness is the ability to regulate one's behavior during communication, the ability to formulate one's own desires and requirements, the ability to satisfy them, the ability to "hear" what others want, as well as the ability to treat oneself with respect and love (to be). self-esteem). A person who behaves firmly is able to clearly formulate what is being discussed, how he sees the situation, what he thinks about it, how he experiences it. He is confident enough, knows how to listen to others and compromise.

Assertiveness is a harmonious combination of a person's personality traits, a manifestation of his knowledge of human nature, skills and communication abilities, which is morally acceptable in a particular situation.

Self-assertiveness means solving a specific issue or problem, realizing and understanding other people involved in it, not violating their interests, and protecting the interests of your side intelligently and skillfully.

Kha.A. Ivanov considers communicative competence to be "the ability to set and solve certain types of communication tasks", as a result, determine the goals of communication, assess the situation, take into account the partner's intentions and communication methods, choose adequate communication strategies, evaluate the success of communication, be ready to change their actions" [7]. The analysis of A.B. Dorbovich's thoughts on communicative competence as a constant readiness for communication shows that the scientist considers it from the point of view of consciousness, thinking: a person thinks, and this means that he lives in a dialogue mode, while a person must always take into account the changing situation in their In addition to intuitive expectations, it should be taken into account according to the expectations of the partner [3].

V.A. Kan-Kalik, N.D. Nikandrov defined communicative competence as a component of human existence that exists in all types of human activity [9]. The

problem, they say, is that not everyone can imagine how certain communicative actions can be performed. It follows that in order to carry out these communicative actions, it is necessary to have certain knowledge, skills and competences.

In fact, the basis for revealing the meaning of the concept of "communicative competence" is E.V. Sidorenko stated that "if we distinguish what is relevant to competence from the definition of competence, then there will be abilities, skills and knowledge that are sufficient and adequate to what is needed in accordance with the components of communicative competence."

Thus, communicative competence is considered by E. V. Sidorenko as a system of internal resources necessary for building an effective communicative action in certain interaction situations.

The problem of formation of communicative competence of a person is reflected in many social, psychological and linguistic studies from different perspectives. The analysis of scientific and theoretical literature shows that only certain issues of the formation of professional communication have been solved: the problems of modeling professional direction and the problems of modeling language activity are analyzed. Effective formation of communicative competence in future public security officers is especially important for them to interact with all layers of the population. In turn, it is necessary to pay attention to the formation of the ability to interact with a group of people and the development of communication skills.

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